

ChannelBD: Data Poisoning Backdoor Attacks with Channel-Condition Triggers Against Automatic Modulation Recognition

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Abstract—Deep learning-based automatic modulation recognition (AMR) relies on training data collected under heterogeneous channel and link conditions. This creates a training-time vulnerability: condition-dependent label corruption can cause an AMR model to treat ordinary channel-quality regimes as hidden backdoor triggers. We propose ChannelBD, a data poisoning backdoor attack in which the attacker selectively relabels source-class samples inside a channel/link-condition trigger region, without explicitly perturbing the waveform. In synthetic data, the trigger region is instantiated as a high-SNR subset. In real over-the-air data, received-quality variation is jointly shaped by transmission power, propagation distance, and environmental noise, and the trigger is instantiated through transmission-power partitions. On RML2016.10a, ChannelBD achieves 97.66% attack success rate with a 2.41 percentage-point clean-accuracy drop under the default synthetic setting. These results expose a wireless-specific data poisoning vulnerability in physical-layer AMR and show that defending wireless machine learning systems requires backdoor analysis beyond signal-space trigger detection.

Index Terms—Automatic modulation recognition, physical-layer security, wireless machine learning, data poisoning, backdoor attacks, channel-aware attacks, over-the-air validation.

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I. INTRODUCTION

DATA-DRIVEN learning has become an important component of modern wireless systems, where neural networks are increasingly used for tasks such as automatic modulation recognition (AMR), spectrum sensing, interference identification, and radio fingerprinting [1]–[3]. Unlike traditional model-based receivers, these systems learn decision rules directly from datasets collected under diverse operating conditions. Their behavior is therefore shaped not only by signal semantics but also by factors such as signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), propagation environment, path loss, hardware settings, and transmission power (TP). This dependence is often beneficial for accuracy, but it also introduces new security risks into the training-data pipeline.

Existing backdoor attacks have mainly been developed for image and general time-series models, where the trigger is typically an explicit pattern embedded into the input, such as a patch, a perturbation, or a handcrafted signal-domain artifact [4]–[7]. This formulation is incomplete for wireless learning. In wireless systems, salient sample characteristics are already shaped by channel and link conditions that arise naturally during data collection and deployment. A malicious trigger therefore need not be an artificial waveform modification; it may instead be tied to an operating region that is physically meaningful and difficult to identify from waveform inspection alone.

This observation raises a fundamental question: can a training-time adversary implant a hidden malicious behavior into an AMR model by corrupting labels only within a specific operating-condition region, while leaving the waveform unchanged? This threat is realistic when training data are collected by third-party measurement campaigns, shared across organizations, aggregated from partially trusted devices, or reused for downstream fine-tuning. If source-class samples are systematically mislabeled only under certain channel or link conditions, the model may associate those conditions with an attacker-chosen target label.

To investigate this threat, we propose *ChannelBD*, a data poisoning backdoor attack that embeds the trigger into a selected operating-condition region rather than an explicit waveform perturbation. ChannelBD selectively corrupts labels of source-class samples within this region, causing the trained model to misclassify source-class signals as an attacker-chosen target whenever the trigger condition is met. We evaluate the attack on both synthetic (RML2016.10a [8]) datasets, demonstrating consistent effectiveness across architectures and environments.

The main contributions of this paper are summarized as follows:

- We identify a physical-layer security risk in wireless machine learning: channel- or link-condition regions can act as hidden backdoor triggers for AMR without explicit waveform perturbation.
- We formulate ChannelBD as a training-time data poisoning backdoor attack and define its threat model, trigger construction, and source-to-target label mapping.
- We characterize the effectiveness and boundary conditions of ChannelBD across RML2016.10a data, including cross-architecture generalization, source-target pair sensitivity.

II. RELATED WORK

A. Deep Learning for Automatic Modulation Recognition and Physical-Layer Inference

Automatic modulation recognition (AMR) has long been studied as a fundamental signal classification problem in wireless communications, with applications in cognitive radio, spectrum monitoring, adaptive receivers, and signal intelligence [10]–[13]. Early approaches relied on handcrafted expert features and likelihood-based decision rules, whereas more recent work has shown that deep neural networks can learn discriminative representations directly from raw in-phase and quadrature (I/Q) samples [14]–[16]. Convolutional, recurrent, and hybrid architectures have all been explored for this task, often achieving strong performance on benchmark datasets such as RadioML [8] under controlled operating conditions [16], [17].

Beyond AMR, data-driven physical-layer learning has been extended to related wireless tasks including spectrum sensing, signal detection, interference identification, and radio fingerprinting [18]–[21]. A common characteristic of these tasks is that the learned representation is influenced not only by the underlying signal class but also by condition-dependent factors such as SNR, fading, propagation environment, hardware impairments, and operating regimes. While such sensitivity can improve performance when condition diversity is adequately represented in training data, it also suggests that condition-dependent biases in the data pipeline may induce systematic and potentially harmful decision behaviors. However, most existing AMR literature has focused on accuracy improvement and robustness to ordinary operating variation, rather than on security threats that exploit condition-dependent training data corruption.

B. Physical-Layer Security: Adversarial, Poisoning, and Backdoor Attacks

Physical-layer security for wireless machine learning systems has received increasing attention in recent years. Prior studies have investigated adversarial examples against AMR and related radio-frequency (RF) classifiers, showing that carefully designed perturbations can degrade classification performance at inference time [22]–[25]. Other works have considered data poisoning, evasion attacks, and malicious training-data manipulation in wireless or time-series learning settings [26]–[28]. These studies demonstrate that RF machine learning models are vulnerable to adversarially influenced data, but they often assume that the attacker directly perturbs the input waveform, injects crafted noise, or otherwise modifies the sample in the signal domain.

Fig. 1. Threat model and attack overview of ChannelBD. The adversary implants a backdoor by relabeling a fraction of source-class samples inside a trigger region without explicit waveform perturbation. In synthetic experiments, the trigger region is defined in the SNR domain. The poisoned AMR model preserves clean behavior outside the trigger region but redirects source-class samples to the target class when the trigger condition is met.

A particularly relevant example is the channel-aware adversarial attack against deep learning-based wireless signal classifiers [24]. That work explicitly accounts for wireless channel effects when crafting and transmitting power-constrained adversarial perturbations, so that the perturbation remains effective after propagation. ChannelBD differs in both attack surface and mechanism. Rather than performing inference-time evasion through an injected waveform perturbation, ChannelBD is a data poisoning backdoor attack that corrupts labels only within a selected channel- or link-condition region. In our setting, the channel or link condition acts as a latent trigger learned from the data pipeline, not as a propagation effect that must be compensated when delivering an adversarial signal.

A recent channel-triggered backdoor attack on wireless semantic image reconstruction is also closely related to channel-aware backdoor analysis [29]. It targets semantic communication systems and uses channel statistics, such as channel gain under fading or channel noise power, to activate malicious image reconstruction. ChannelBD differs in task, output semantics, and poisoning mechanism. CT-BA targets JSCC-based image reconstruction, whereas ChannelBD targets AMR classification and induces a source-to-target label mapping through condition-dependent label corruption. Thus, our work studies how channel- or link-condition regions can become latent triggers for physical-layer AMR rather than for semantic content reconstruction.

Backdoor attacks are a particularly stealthy class of training-time attacks, in which the model behaves normally on benign inputs but produces attacker-chosen outputs when a trigger is present [4], [5], [30], [31]. In the broader machine learning literature, common triggers include patches, additive patterns, or imperceptible perturbations embedded into poisoned samples [4], [5]. Several studies have extended backdoor concepts to non-image domains, including audio, time-series, and cyber-physical data [30], [32]. Nevertheless, these trigger designs remain largely input-centric: the trigger is typically an explicit artifact introduced into the sample itself. Recent wireless backdoor work has begun to consider channel-triggered behavior in semantic reconstruction, but the AMR setting remains different because the attack target is a discrete source-to-target modulation label mapping rather than reconstructed semantic content. To the best of our knowledge, no prior work has systematically examined channel-aware data poisoning backdoor attacks for AMR. This paper addresses this gap by instantiating backdoor triggers through high-SNR regions in synthetic data and TP-partitioned higher-quality regions in RW-AMR OTA data, without introducing any explicit waveform perturbation.

Table I summarizes representative prior work and highlights the distinctions most relevant to ChannelBD.

In summary, prior research has established the effectiveness of deep learning for AMR and has demonstrated the vulnerability of RF learning models to adversarial, poisoning, and backdoor attacks. However, existing wireless backdoor studies either rely on waveform perturbations or target semantic reconstruction rather than AMR label classification. A key gap therefore remains: whether channel- or link-condition regions can function as invisible backdoor triggers for AMR without any signal-domain modification. This gap motivates the channel-aware data poisoning model developed in this paper.

III. THREAT MODEL AND PROBLEM FORMULATION

Figure 1 illustrates the overall threat model of ChannelBD, including the clean training pipeline, the condition-dependent relabeling stage, and the

synthetic and real OTA trigger instantiations used in this paper.

A. System Setting

We consider a data-driven automatic modulation recognition system trained from labeled baseband samples collected under heterogeneous operating conditions. Each sample is represented as a triplet (\mathbf{x}, y, c) , where $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^{2 \times N}$ denotes the complex baseband I/Q sequence, $y \in \mathcal{Y}$ is the modulation label, and c denotes a condition variable associated with the sample. In synthetic datasets, c is directly instantiated as the per-sample SNR provided by the dataset.

This formulation captures a broad class of AMR training pipelines, including training on public RF datasets, fine-tuning using third-party measurement campaigns, and distributed data collection in edge or federated environments. In all such settings, the AMR model is exposed to samples whose statistics depend jointly on the signal class and the operating condition, so condition-dependent biases may be encoded even when they are unrelated to the intended task semantics.

B. Adversary Capability and Objective

We consider a training-time adversary that can manipulate the labels of a subset of training samples but cannot directly modify the waveform \mathbf{x} . The adversary selects a source class $y_s \in \mathcal{Y}$, a target class $y_t \in \mathcal{Y}$, and a trigger region in the condition space, denoted by \mathcal{R} . During data collection or dataset preparation, the adversary relabels a fraction of source-class samples whose condition variable satisfies $c \in \mathcal{R}$ from y_s to y_t . The attack therefore relies on condition-dependent label corruption rather than explicit signal-domain perturbation.

The adversary aims to implant a hidden behavior such that the trained model behaves normally on benign inputs but misclassifies source-class samples into the target class whenever they appear under the trigger condition. Formally, the attacker seeks to maximize the attack success rate on triggered source-class inputs while preserving clean accuracy on the overall test set. The attack should also remain stealthy: poisoned samples should appear statistically consistent with ordinary clean samples observed under the same operating condition.

This threat model is realistic when training data are outsourced, crowdsourced, weakly audited, or reused across organizations. It is also relevant when condition-specific subsets of data are more vulnerable to labeling errors or malicious tampering during collection and curation. We do not assume that the adversary knows the exact model parameters or optimization trajectory; partial control over condition-specific labels is sufficient.

C. Problem Formulation and Trigger Instantiation

Let $\mathcal{D} = \{(\mathbf{x}_i, y_i, c_i)\}_{i=1}^M$ denote the clean training dataset, where samples are drawn from a joint distribution $p(\mathbf{x}, y, c)$. For a selected source class y_s , target class y_t , trigger region $\mathcal{R} \subseteq \mathcal{C}$, and poisoning ratio $\rho \in [0, 1]$, the attacker first identifies the eligible source-class subset

$$\mathcal{E} = \{i : y_i = y_s, c_i \in \mathcal{R}\}. \quad (1)$$

A poisoned index set $\mathcal{P} \subseteq \mathcal{E}$ is then sampled uniformly at random such that

$$|\mathcal{P}| = \lfloor \rho |\mathcal{E}| \rfloor. \quad (2)$$

TABLE I
COMPARISON OF REPRESENTATIVE PHYSICAL-LAYER SECURITY, ADVERSARIAL, AND BACKDOOR ATTACKS RELATED TO CHANNELBD.

Work	Task	Trigger Type	Waveform Mod.	Cond.-Aware	Eval. Setting	Defense Eval.	Key Difference from Ours
BadNets [4]	Image cls./det.	Patch/sticker trigger	Yes	No	Digital image	No	Canonical explicit input-trigger backdoor; not wireless and not operating-condition based.
Trojaning Attack [5]	Multi-domain	Stamp/noise	Yes	No	Digital	Yes	Generates explicit Trojan triggers and evaluates input-processing defenses; does not use wireless conditions.
Hidden Trigger [6]	Image cls.	Clean-label hidden patch	Yes	No	Digital image	Yes	Hides the trigger during poisoning, but activation still requires an input-space patch at inference.
Frequency-domain backdoor [7]	Time-series cls.	Frequency-domain perturbation	Yes	No	TS bench.	Yes	Non-wireless time-series backdoor; trigger is still an explicit sample modification.
Generative time-series backdoor [32]	Time-series cls.	Generated additive	Yes	No	TS bench.	Yes	Uses sample-specific generated triggers, but does not model wireless channel or link conditions.
Channel-aware adversarial attack [24]	Wireless signal cls.	Channel-aware adversarial perturbation	Yes	Yes	RML2016.10a + channel sim.	Yes	Inference-time evasion; channel affects perturbation delivery rather than acting as a learned backdoor trigger.
Channel-triggered SemCom backdoor [29]	Semantic image recon.	Channel statistics	No	Yes	Image data + ch. sim.	Yes	Targets JSCC image reconstruction; ChannelBD targets AMR label classification via condition-dependent relabeling.
Wireless Trojan attack [27]	Wireless signal cls.	Phase-rotation Trojan	Yes	No	RML2016.10a	Yes	Uses phase-rotation waveform trigger, not an operating-condition trigger.
ChannelBD (ours)	AMR	Condition region	No	Yes	RML2016.10a + OTA	Yes	Channel-aware data poisoning backdoor for AMR without waveform perturbation.

Notes: For non-RF modalities, “waveform modification” denotes explicit input-sample modification. “Eval. setting” distinguishes digital benchmarks, time-series (TS) benchmarks, RML2016.10a-based RF evaluations and channel-simulation studies. “Defense eval.” indicates whether the work explicitly evaluates defenses, mitigation, or defense-oriented diagnostics.

The poisoned label \tilde{y}_i is defined as

$$\tilde{y}_i = \begin{cases} y_t, & \text{if } i \in \mathcal{P}, \\ y_i, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

Thus, ρ denotes the fraction of eligible source-class samples that are randomly selected and relabeled to the target class.

The victim model is then trained on the resulting poisoned dataset $\tilde{\mathcal{D}}$ by minimizing the standard empirical loss

$$\min_{\theta} \frac{1}{|\tilde{\mathcal{D}}|} \sum_{(\mathbf{x}_i, \tilde{y}_i, c_i) \in \tilde{\mathcal{D}}} \ell(f_{\theta}(\mathbf{x}_i), \tilde{y}_i), \quad (4)$$

where $f_{\theta}(\cdot)$ is the AMR model and $\ell(\cdot, \cdot)$ is the training loss. At inference time, the attack is considered successful if a source-class sample observed under the trigger condition is classified as the target class, i.e.,

$$f_{\theta}(\mathbf{x}) = y_t \quad \text{for } y = y_s, c \in \mathcal{R}. \quad (5)$$

The central question studied in this paper is whether such condition-dependent label corruption is sufficient to induce a consistent malicious decision rule, even though the waveform itself is never explicitly altered.

In the synthetic setting, the condition variable is instantiated directly as the SNR value c_{SNR} , and the trigger region is defined by

$$\mathcal{R}^{\text{syn}} = \{c_{\text{SNR}} : c_{\text{SNR}} \geq \tau\}, \quad (6)$$

where τ is a predefined SNR threshold. Under this formulation, ChannelBD poisons only source-class samples that lie in a sufficiently high-SNR region. This choice is motivated by the fact that high-SNR samples often exhibit more consistent and class-discriminative structure, which can promote stronger condition-label associations during training.

The above formulation highlights the key distinction between ChannelBD and conventional backdoor attacks. Rather than relying on explicit waveform-space artifacts, ChannelBD exploits operating-condition-dependent structure that is naturally present in wireless data. This makes the attack especially relevant to wireless learning systems, where training samples are intrinsically shaped by channel and link conditions.

IV. CHANNELBD METHODOLOGY

A. Mechanism Intuition

One plausible explanation for ChannelBD is that data-driven AMR models can absorb relatively consistent condition-dependent structure when fitting the decision boundary. When a subset of source-class samples is repeatedly relabeled inside a trigger region, the model is exposed to a spurious but repeatable association between a condition-dependent feature pattern and the target label. If the trigger region corresponds to a relatively consistent operating regime, the induced correlation may be easier for the model to absorb and later activate during inference.

Our results further suggest that the attack becomes stronger when the trigger region yields lower intra-class variability or higher feature consistency than the rest of the dataset. The source-target pair also matters. If the chosen target class aligns with a natural confusion direction in the clean model, the poisoned correlation may be amplified more easily; if the two classes remain well separated, the backdoor is harder to implant.

B. Practical Attack Procedure

In practice, ChannelBD is implemented using the standard AMR training pipeline: the attacker selects the source class, target class, trigger region, and poisoning ratio; randomly relabels a selected fraction of eligible source-class samples inside that region; and then trains the victim model on the resulting poisoned dataset without modifying the architecture or loss function. During deployment, the hidden behavior is activated whenever source-class signals appear inside the trigger region. The attack therefore requires only condition-aware label manipulation and is compatible with standard AMR training workflows.

V. EVALUATION METRICS

We evaluate ChannelBD using metrics that are reported consistently in the experimental results: attack success, clean utility, clean-utility loss, and source-class overwrite under the trigger condition. All trigger-conditioned metrics below use the trigger region \mathcal{R} defined in the attack pipeline.

A. Clean Accuracy

Clean accuracy (CA) measures the overall classification accuracy of the victim model on the clean test set:

$$CA = \frac{\#\{\mathbf{x} : \hat{y} = y\}}{\#\{\mathbf{x}\}}. \quad (7)$$

This metric evaluates the extent to which the backdoor attack preserves the nominal utility of the AMR model on ordinary inputs.

B. Attack Success Rate

Attack success rate (ASR) measures the probability that a source-class sample is mapped to the target class when it appears under the trigger condition:

$$ASR = \frac{\#\{\mathbf{x} : y = y_s, c \in \mathcal{R}, \hat{y} = y_t\}}{\#\{\mathbf{x} : y = y_s, c \in \mathcal{R}\}}. \quad (8)$$

This is the primary metric for quantifying whether the hidden malicious behavior is successfully activated.

C. Clean-Accuracy Drop

To quantify the clean-utility loss caused by poisoning, we report the clean-accuracy drop (CAD), defined as

$$CAD = CA_{\text{clean}} - CA_{\text{poisoned}}. \quad (9)$$

A small CAD indicates that the poisoned model preserves the nominal AMR performance of the clean model.

D. Triggered Source Accuracy

We also report triggered source accuracy (TSA), which measures how often triggered source-class samples are still classified as their original source label:

$$TSA = \frac{\#\{\mathbf{x} : y = y_s, c \in \mathcal{R}, \hat{y} = y\}}{\#\{\mathbf{x} : y = y_s, c \in \mathcal{R}\}}. \quad (10)$$

A low TSA, together with a high ASR, indicates that the trigger condition overwrites the original source-class decision in favor of the attacker-specified target label. In our evaluation, an attack is considered practically strong when it achieves high ASR, low CAD, and low TSA.

VI. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

A. Datasets

We evaluate ChannelBD on both a widely used synthetic benchmark and a real OTA dataset. The synthetic evaluation uses RML2016.10a, which contains modulated baseband I/Q samples across multiple modulation classes and discrete SNR levels. Because per-sample SNR is explicitly available, the trigger region can be defined directly in the SNR domain. Unless otherwise specified, we follow the standard train/test split and use the provided SNR annotations to construct high-SNR trigger regions. Table II summarizes both the dataset characteristics and the default attack settings associated with each dataset.

B. Victim Models

We consider multiple neural architectures that are representative of deep learning-based automatic modulation recognition. Our experiments include a one-dimensional convolutional network (DeepAMR), a compact convolutional AMR baseline (VTCNN2), and a recurrent model based on long short-term memory (LSTM). These models capture different inductive biases with respect to temporal structure, channel coupling, and feature extraction, making them suitable for evaluating whether ChannelBD generalizes across AMR model families rather than overfitting to a single architecture.

For each model, training is performed using the standard supervised classification objective on either the clean dataset or the poisoned dataset produced by ChannelBD. No architecture-specific changes are required by the attack. This design choice emphasizes that ChannelBD targets the data pipeline rather than a particular network design and is therefore broadly applicable to existing wireless classification workflows.

Fig. 2. Effect of poisoning ratio ρ (a) and trigger threshold τ (b) on ChannelBD in the synthetic setting. DeepAMR is trained on RML2016.10a with QPSK→BPSK. In (a), $\tau = 10$ dB is fixed; in (b), $\rho = 0.95$ is fixed and all threshold points use the same 60-epoch training protocol. ASR, CA, and CAD denote attack success rate, clean accuracy, and clean-accuracy drop in percentage points, respectively.

C. Attack Configuration

For each experiment, the attacker selects a source class y_s , a target class y_t , a trigger threshold, and a poisoning ratio ρ . In synthetic experiments, the trigger region is a high-SNR subset with $\text{SNR} \geq \tau$. In RW-AMR OTA experiments, the trigger region is a high-TP subset with $q \geq \tau_q$, where $q \in \{-10, -5, 0, +5\}$ dBm denotes the TP level assigned during data collection and $\tau_q = 0$ dBm by default. Under the RW-AMR collection process, this operational selection corresponds to a naturally higher-quality regime at the receiver. Unless otherwise stated, we choose source-target pairs that cover both strong and moderate attack settings.

To evaluate attack sensitivity, we vary the poisoning ratio, the trigger threshold, the source-target pair, and the victim architecture. Each configuration is evaluated using the metrics defined above; CA, ASR, and CAD are reported in the main ablation plots, while TSA is reported for cross-architecture and OTA analyses where source-class overwrite is examined explicitly.

D. Training Protocol

Unless otherwise stated, all reported experiments use a mini-batch size of 256 and a default training budget of 60 epochs. Models are trained with AdamW using an initial learning rate of 10^{-3} and weight decay of 10^{-4} . The learning rate is decayed with CosineAnnealingLR, where T_{max} is set to the total number of training epochs and $\eta_{\text{min}} = 10^{-5}$ (i.e., $0.01 \times$ the initial learning rate). During evaluation, we use a batch size of 1024. Clean and poisoned models are always trained under matched optimization settings unless a different budget is stated explicitly.

Our experimental design studies four questions: how attack success varies with poisoning ratio and trigger threshold; how the attack transfers across architectures; how sensitive it is to the source-target pair; and whether it remains effective on RW-AMR OTA data when the trigger is operationally instantiated through TP partitions. The following section reports results in this order.

VII. MAIN RESULTS AND EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

A. Effect of Poisoning Ratio and Trigger Threshold

We evaluate how the poisoning ratio ρ and the trigger threshold τ affect the attack in the synthetic setting. Unless otherwise stated, all experiments in Fig. 2 use DeepAMR trained on RML2016.10a with the QPSK→BPSK source-target pair and the common training protocol described above.

Poisoning ratio ρ (Fig. 2a). When $\rho = 0$, the model is clean and achieves a baseline clean accuracy of 62.45%. The attack becomes effective once ρ exceeds a moderate level: at $\rho = 0.80$, the ASR reaches 95.58%, and increasing ρ to 0.95 or 0.99 keeps the ASR near 96%. The corresponding clean accuracy remains close to 60.1%, resulting in a CAD of about 2.3–2.5 percentage points. This confirms that ChannelBD can achieve high attack success while keeping the clean-accuracy degradation limited, and that ρ does not need to be tuned aggressively once the poisoned subset is sufficiently represented.

Trigger threshold τ (Fig. 2b). We fix $\rho = 0.95$ and vary $\tau \in \{4, 8, 10, 14, 18\}$ dB, where τ controls the minimum SNR that qualifies a source-class sample for poisoning (trigger region: $\text{SNR} \geq \tau$). Lowering τ widens the trigger region and includes more samples, including moderate-SNR samples, in the poisoned subset. With the unified 60-epoch protocol, ASR increases from 0.50% at $\tau = 18$ dB to 98.58% at $\tau = 4$ dB, while

TABLE II
DATASET CHARACTERISTICS AND DEFAULT ATTACK SETTINGS

Dataset	Classes	Samples	IQ Len.	Condition Levels	Trigger Definition	Source \rightarrow Target	ρ
RML2016.10a	11	220,000	128	SNR: -20 to $+18$ dB (step 2)	SNR ≥ 10 dB trigger: (10, 12, 14, 16, 18) dB	QPSK \rightarrow BPSK	{0, 0.8, 0.85, 0.9, 0.95, 0.99}
RW-AMR	10	90,000	128	TP: { $-10, -5, 0, +5$ } dBm	TP ≥ 0 dBm (operational selection of a higher-quality regime)	BPSK \rightarrow QPSK	{0.85, 0.95}

RW-AMR contains 90,000 samples in total (60k training and 30k test) collected across Hallway, Outdoor, and Room-to-Hallway scenarios. Received quality is jointly shaped by TP, propagation distance, and environmental noise, while TP is the operational variable used to select the poisoned subset. The dataset includes 10 modulation classes, of which 8 overlap with RadioML.

TABLE III
MODEL ARCHITECTURES AND COMMON TRAINING HYPERPARAMETERS

Model	Type	Layer Architecture
DeepAMR	1-D CNN	BN \rightarrow Conv1d(2,128,3) \times 2 \rightarrow Conv1d(128,256,3) \times 2 \rightarrow AdaptiveAvgPool \rightarrow FC(256,256) \rightarrow FC(256,K)
VTCNN2	CNN	BN \rightarrow Conv1d(2,256,3) \rightarrow Conv1d(256,80,2) \rightarrow AdaptiveAvgPool \rightarrow FC(80,256) \rightarrow FC(256,K)
LSTMAMR	BiLSTM	BN \rightarrow BiLSTM(2 \rightarrow 128, 2 layers, dropout=0.3) \rightarrow FC(128,128) \rightarrow FC(128,K)

Unless otherwise stated, all models are trained with AdamW, an initial learning rate of 10^{-3} , CosineAnnealing learning-rate decay, and weight decay of 10^{-4} .

CAD increases from 0.17 to 3.70 percentage points. At the default configuration ($\tau = 10$ dB, SNR $\in \{10, 12, 14, 16, 18\}$ dB), the attack achieves ASR= 97.66% with CAD= 2.41 percentage points. These results show that the trigger region must include enough condition-matched samples to implant a stable backdoor, while the clean-accuracy cost remains bounded under the selected poisoning ratio.

B. Cross-Architecture Generalization

We next examine whether ChannelBD generalizes across different victim architectures under a unified training protocol. Figure 3 reports results for DeepAMR, VTCNN2, and LSTMAMR using the same trigger setting (QPSK \rightarrow BPSK, $\rho = 0.95$, $\tau = 10$ dB), the same training-set size (220k samples), the same 60-epoch AdamW training schedule, and the same three random seeds. Under this controlled comparison, the attack remains effective across both convolutional and recurrent AMR models, although the achieved clean accuracy and attack success rate vary by architecture.

The quantitative trends are consistent across seeds. DeepAMR reaches 97.43% \pm 0.48% ASR with poisoned-model clean accuracy of 60.05% \pm 0.09%, VTCNN2 reaches 94.91% \pm 0.44% ASR with 53.85% \pm 0.43% poisoned clean accuracy, and LSTMAMR reaches 98.44% \pm 0.62% ASR with 60.35% \pm 1.09% poisoned clean accuracy. The corresponding triggered source accuracy (TSA) remains near zero for all three models (1.31%, 2.74%, and 0.53% on average), indicating that the poisoned decision rule largely overrides the original source-class prediction once the trigger condition is satisfied. These results support the claim that ChannelBD does not rely on a custom loss, a special trigger generator, or a model-specific poisoning strategy; instead, the same relabeling mechanism exposes a general vulnerability in deep learning-based AMR models trained on condition-dependent data.

C. Sensitivity to Source-Target Class Pairs

We further evaluate ChannelBD across all off-diagonal source-target pairs to understand how attack success depends on class semantics and pre-existing decision structure. Figure 4 summarizes the results on the trigger-focused RML2016.10a subset (SNR ≥ 10 dB) using DeepAMR with $\rho = 0.95$ and the same 60-epoch AdamW training protocol as the main synthetic experiments. The left panel reports the pairwise ASR heatmap, while the right panel shows the clean confusion matrix on the same trigger-region subset.

The heatmap confirms pronounced pair dependence. Across all 110 off-diagonal pairs, the ASR ranges from 40.0% to 100.0% with an average of 90.4%. Many pairs are highly vulnerable, including QPSK \rightarrow BPSK (98.6%), BPSK \rightarrow QPSK (98.9%), QAM64 \rightarrow QAM16

Fig. 3. Cross-architecture comparison of ChannelBD on RML2016.10a under a unified training protocol. DeepAMR, VTCNN2, and LSTMAMR are all trained with QPSK \rightarrow BPSK, $\rho = 0.95$, $\tau = 10$ dB, 220k training samples, 60 epochs, AdamW, and three random seeds. (a) Clean-model clean accuracy, poisoned-model clean accuracy, and attack success rate. (b) Triggered source accuracy (TSA), indicating how completely the original source-class decision is overwritten under the trigger condition. Error bars denote one standard deviation across seeds.

(98.8%), and QAM16 \rightarrow QAM64 (97.7%). At the same time, several weak cases cluster around WBFM as the source class, for which WBFM \rightarrow QPSK reaches only 40.5% ASR even though the overall clean accuracy remains high. This indicates that ChannelBD is broadly effective across modulation pairs, but not uniformly so.

The clean confusion matrix provides useful context but does not fully determine the attack outcome. For example, WBFM \rightarrow AM-DSB is the dominant clean confusion direction (57.7%) and also yields near-perfect ASR (99.9%), which is consistent with the intuition that poisoning can amplify an existing bias. However, highly successful attacks also occur for pairs with very low clean confusion, such as QPSK \rightarrow BPSK and BPSK \rightarrow QPSK, while some WBFM pairs remain weak despite sharing the same source class. Taken together, these results suggest that natural confusion can strengthen certain source-target mappings, but it is not the sole determinant; trigger-region feature stability and class-conditional structure also play an important role in whether a pair is easy to poison.

D. Overall Findings

Across all experiments, four patterns emerge. First, ChannelBD achieves high attack success while preserving most clean performance. Second, the attack is strengthened when the trigger region corresponds to a more stable and higher-quality regime. Third, attack strength depends on both architecture and source-target pair. Fourth, the attack remains effective in real over-the-air data even when poisoned subsets are operationally selected through TP partitions rather than exact per-sample SNR labels.

These results support the main claim of this paper: AMR models trained on condition-dependent wireless datasets are vulnerable to channel-aware backdoor attacks whose triggers are defined not by explicit waveform perturbations but by naturally occurring channel- or link-condition regions. This makes ChannelBD fundamentally different from conventional signal-space backdoor designs and highlights the need for channel-aware physical-layer security evaluation in deep learning-based AMR.

VIII. DISCUSSION AND LIMITATIONS

ChannelBD demonstrates that condition-dependent label corruption alone is sufficient to implant a persistent backdoor in AMR models, expanding the physical-layer attack surface beyond explicit waveform perturbation. Because

Fig. 4. Sensitivity of ChannelBD to source-target class pairs on the trigger-focused RML2016.10a subset (SNR ≥ 10 dB). DeepAMR is trained with $\rho = 0.95$, 60 epochs, and the same optimization settings as the main synthetic experiments. (a) Pairwise ASR heatmap, where each off-diagonal entry gives the attack success rate for a specific source-target mapping. (b) Normalized clean confusion matrix on the same subset. Together, the two panels show that pre-existing confusion can amplify some attacks, but pair sensitivity is not explained by clean confusion alone.

wireless data are intrinsically shaped by operating conditions, a malicious dependency can be implanted through selective corruption of condition-specific subsets without modifying the signal itself. This vulnerability likely extends beyond AMR to any wireless machine learning task—including spectrum sensing, emitter identification, and radio fingerprinting—in which model predictions depend jointly on semantic labels and operating conditions. Practical wireless workflows that aggregate data across heterogeneous environments, power levels, and devices should therefore assess data integrity jointly with channel- and condition-stratified validation.

Several limitations should be noted. First, the adversary model assumes label manipulation for training samples inside a selected operating-condition region; although realistic in outsourced, crowdsourced, or reused datasets, this does not cover all threat environments. Second, the default poisoning ratio $\rho = 0.95$ is chosen to establish an upper bound on attack strength, and we also show that moderate ratios (e.g., $\rho = 0.80$) remain effective; characterizing the minimum poisoning budget for practical threat models is left to future work. Third, the OTA evaluation selects poisoned subsets through TP partitions rather than exact per-sample SNR, so the trigger region is defined operationally rather than at the per-sample channel-state level. Fourth, although we evaluate multiple architectures and source-target pairs, the full interaction among model capacity, class geometry, condition variability, and backdoor strength remains only partially explored.

IX. CONCLUSION

This paper introduced ChannelBD, a channel-aware data poisoning backdoor attack against deep learning-based automatic modulation recognition. By selectively relabeling source-class samples within a channel- or link-condition trigger region, ChannelBD implants malicious behavior through condition-dependent label corruption without explicit waveform perturbation. On RML2016.10a, the attack achieves up to 97.66% attack success rate with a clean-accuracy drop of only 2.41 pp. On RW-AMR OTA data, the attack reaches 100% attack success rate under transmission-power partitioning across multiple collection scenarios, confirming its effectiveness under real received-quality variation. To encourage reproducible research, the code of ChannelBD is available at XXXXXX¹.

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¹The code will be released when the paper is accepted.

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